

Teachers as Troubleshooters: Making ICT Lab in School an Active Space for Innovative Teaching and Learning

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Abstract—In India the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have been introduced in the school ecosystem by way of ICT lab or computer lab. However, numerous studies and reports have found that many ICT labs in schools do not function properly. Due to lack of funds and non-availability of technical personnel in the remote and rural areas even a smallest technical glitch renders devices dysfunctional. Even today, the government schools do not have any provision for a computer technician and most of the teachers are still catching up with basic digital literacy skills. Moreover, there is a culture of fear of breaking-down the devices and machines. Therefore, when encountered with an issue no one dares to try to troubleshoot the computing devices thereby rendering a large number of school ICT labs non-functional. With a view to address this challenge and to make the ICT lab in school an active space for innovative and technology enabled teaching-learning we experimented to develop teachers' technical capabilities and attempted to orient teachers as troubleshooters and maintainers of the school ICT lab. As part of a large scale technology integration project in government schools across India we developed and offered a teacher professional development course. Originally designed for a blended mode of instruction, due to covid-19 restrictions, the course was offered in online mode to three cohorts of total 191 in-service government school teachers in the states of Telangana, Chhattisgarh and Mizoram. The course was offered over six weeks and included synchronous online sessions and asynchronous activities of hands-on/practical nature which needed to be shared on a learning management system. Based on the assessment performance a substantially high number of course participants (77.45%) successfully completed the course and received the certificates. This paper outlines the design of the course and its implementation with the three cohorts. Analyzing the data generated by online course platform, feedback by course participants and experiences of course designers/instructors, the paper examines the viability of the model of 'teacher as a troubleshooter' to sustain ICT lab in schools and suggests recommendations for the future.

Keywords—school ICT lab, ICT in education, teacher professional development, teachers as troubleshooters

I. INTRODUCTION

With the pervasive and inescapable use of computers and technology in education there appears a broad consensus on the need for teachers to develop capabilities and professional competence to teach with technology. In the technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) framework [1] Harris, Mishra and Koehler have argued that in addition to the essential pedagogical and content knowledge (PCK), teachers now need to cultivate technological knowledge too, in order to effectively integrate technology in everyday teaching. The National Education Policy - 2020 of India [2] recognizes the need for teachers' professional development

in technology enabled teaching and learning as well as the need to create supportive infrastructure. Similarly it has been widely emphasized that teachers as drivers of educative process in the school ecosystem need to develop information and communication technology (ICT) literacy and digital competencies that could range from awareness to ability to effectively use and even create thoughtful content that could engender innovative pedagogical practices and better learning outcomes [3], [4], [5].

While there have been multifarious efforts to upskill teachers with ICT and digital literacy skills there is a burgeoning challenge that is creating hindrance to the efforts of technology integration in education - the lack of technical maintenance and malfunctioning of computer devices in the school ICT lab. This is a crucial issue. Because in India the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have been introduced in the school ecosystem by way of ICT lab or computer lab. An ICT lab is generally a dedicated room with 10 or more computers connected in a local area network (LAN). Sometimes the lab is equipped with a projecting device such as a projector or a digital display screen, and internet connectivity. Seldomly the classrooms are equipped with any technology. That means the technology use and integration in the teaching-learning process is dependent on the functioning of the ICT lab in school. Numerous studies and reports have found that many ICT labs in schools do not function properly [6], [7]. Because, the computers, the software applications installed in them and the peripheral devices in ICT labs frequently malfunction. These devices need regular maintenance and upkeep. And, due to lack of funds and non-availability of technical personnel in the remote and rural areas even a smallest technical glitch renders devices dysfunctional. Even today, the government schools do not have any provision for a computer technician and most of the teachers are still catching up with basic digital literacy skills. Moreover, there is a culture of fear of breaking-down (kharab hona in Hindi). Therefore, when encountered with an issue no one dares to try to troubleshoot the computing devices thereby rendering a large number of school ICT labs non-functional.

With a view to address this challenge and to make the ICT lab in school an active space for innovative and technology enabled teaching-learning we experimented to develop teachers' technical capabilities and attempted to orient teachers as troubleshooters and problem solvers of the school ICT lab. As part of a large scale technology integration project in government schools we developed and offered a teacher professional development course. Originally designed for a blended mode of instruction, due to covid-19 restrictions, the course was offered in online mode

to 191 in-service government school teachers in three different states in India over six weeks during 2021. This paper outlines the design of the course, its implementation with three cohorts and laments on the experiences of course designers/instructors (authors of this papers) and that of the participating teachers. Analyzing the data generated by online course platform, the paper examines the lessons learned and suggests recommendations for similar interventions which may be relatable for the technology enabled/integrated TPD in the global south context.

II. APPROACH AND DESIGN PRINCIPLES

Following the TPACK framework and principles of constructivism and constructionism, the TPD course aimed to develop teachers' technical capabilities with a view to address the challenge of ICT lab maintenance and to make the ICT lab in school an active space for innovative and technology enabled teaching-learning. The course attempted to equip teachers with skill sets to troubleshoot and resolve the commonly encountered technical issues in the school ICT lab.

A. Design of TPD Course

The TPD course named "ICT Lab in school" carrying an academic weightage of 2 credits (corresponding to a total of 50 hours of engagement (15 synchronous + 35 asynchronous hours)) was originally designed for a blended mode of offering (few face-to-face sessions followed by online learning) to be offered over 6 weeks, with 3 days of in person hands-on workshop and subsequent online mode requiring a minimum of 6 hours of weekly engagement by learners.

Fig. 1. Course design - ICT Lab in school a course for teachers.

However, due to COVID-19 pandemic, the course was offered in fully online mode. The course structure and content were revised. The hands-on activities were divided into small chunks and recorded as short video bytes. The assessments also had to be revised with the considerations of blended to online mode of the course. Nevertheless, principles of constructivism and constructionism remained embedded as the activities needed hands-on effort by participants.

With the assumption that the teachers taking the course may have absolutely no knowledge of technology the course content was design as low threshold high ceiling - i.e. the content started introduction to basic technology literacy and then gradually moved to cover more technical details of hardware, software, network and finally the setup of ICT lab in school. Table 1 below outlines the unit wise structuring and assessment components.

TABLE I. COURSE CONTENT AND ASSESSMENT STRUCTURE

Topics	Assessment Activities and Weightage
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Unit 1: Introduction to ICT	Peer Graded ORA (open response assessment) – 5%
Unit 2: Hardware	Three Peer Graded ORA and Three machine graded MCQ/Drag-Drop – 40%
Unit 3: Software	One Peer Graded ORA and Three machine graded MCQ/Drag-Drop – 40%
Unit 4: Maintaining ICT lab in school	One Peer Graded ORA – 15%

The topics ranged from basic introduction of ICT terminologies to functional aspects of networking and troubleshooting computer and network devices in the school ICT lab. The assessment components were of two types: i) to gauge learning and understanding of concepts; and ii) application of understanding through hands-on and learners were to upload proof of their work as actual digital artefact or image/video which were then anonymously peer graded by learners.

The course was offered on the in-house learning management system (LMS) – TISSx <https://www.tissx.tiss.edu> – a customized version of Open edX MOOC platform which could be accessed through a browser based web app (for laptop/desktop) or an android mobile app. As can be observed in Table 1, the course was designed to be hands-on and included many activity based assessments. In order to foster collaboration and peer learning the course thoughtfully leveraged the LMS platform features of discussion forum, peer graded assessment and Telegram based community of practice (CoP). The participants were supposed to achieve passing grades (70%) to receive the course completion certificate. In the next section details of implementation will be discussed.

B. Details of Implementation

The course was offered in online mode to three cohorts of total 191 in-service government school teachers in the states of Telangana (cohort-1), Chhattisgarh (cohort-2) and Mizoram (cohort-3) during the year 2021. For each cohort there was a different course run (instance) on the LMS platform which ran between 6 to 8 weeks. All of the course participants were in-service government school teachers, having different subject specialization, and were nominated by the state government's nodal agency - state council for education research and training (SCERT) as part of a large-scale collaborative EdTech intervention - connected learning initiative (CLix) [8].

The course commenced with 12 synchronous sessions of one hour each for the initial two weeks. The online synchronous sessions covered conceptual aspects of the topics and allowed interaction and opportunities for exchange between course learners and instructors. Subsequently the course participants were engaged on the online course platform (LMS) and through Telegram app based CoP. At the end of the course participants were asked to undertake an online post-course survey (having 20 questions about the course content, structure, learning experience and feedback to instructors) which was strongly encouraged but was voluntary and not tagged to course completion. By making the post course survey voluntary independent of course completion it was hoped to gather genuine and honest responses ensuring reliability and validity of data.

III. COURSE PERFORMANCE DATA, DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

The course yielded some interesting insights. First, this was a unique first of its kind course which aimed to develop government school teachers as technical troubleshooters and

thereby sought to provide a sustainable model for the upkeep and functioning of ICT lab in schools. As shown in Fig 2, the course had a total passing percentage of 77.45% across three cohorts with cohort 1 having a passing percentage of 87.63%. This unusually high passing percentage as compared to general trends of MOOC passing percentage could be attributed to the fact that this course was offered not as a MOOC but as a Small Private Online Course (SPOC). Additionally, since it was mandated by the state government, the teachers had to take the course. There was no choice. Despite this, in view of the subject matter (which was technical in nature) that required teachers to put extra effort to learn and practice, and multiple peer graded assignments (which means the participating teachers had to review anonymous submissions of their peers) such a high passing percentage is a significant achievement.

Fig. 2. Performance of course participants in ICT Lab in School TPD course (Year 2021)

Now, let's look at post course survey results. With the aim of gathering genuine and honest responses the survey was made as voluntary and independent of course completion. However, this had a somewhat adverse effect on the data sample. Only 60/158 of the participants i.e. 38% responded to the survey. The quest for reliability and validity of data seem to have skewed the overall data. Nonetheless, the post course survey results give some interesting insights on the experiences of course participants.

Fig. 3. Did the participants had prior experience of taking an online course and how did participants accessed the course

Out of 60 respondents 39 were from cohort-1, 9 from cohort-2 and 12 participants from cohort-3. 40 Male and 20 female participants responded to the post course survey. Interestingly, for almost half of the respondents (48.3%) this course was the first experience of online learning for professional development (see Fig. 3). And, in terms of devices, half of the respondents had taken the course completely on a smartphone device, while the rest 50% had accessed the course on a laptop or desktop. This is an interesting insight which goes against the popular perception that government school teachers do not have access to laptop or desktop devices.

With regard to the relevance of course content and learnings, a significant majority of respondents (56/60) found the course content very relevant or relevant; Moreover,

61.7% (37/60) respondents said that some of the content was new, whereas only 38.3% (23/60) found all of the content as new. Similarly, while 83.3% (50/60) respondents found the topics, examples and activities given in the course as adequate, 16.7% (10/60) felt the need for more topics and examples. Therefore, it can be inferred that the course content did resonate well with both novice and experienced teachers and teachers do like to understand technical aspects of educational technology.

Can teachers be able to troubleshoot common issues in the school ICT lab and keep it functional? Was the driving question that led to design development and implementation of this course. One possible way to answer this question is to look at the performance of participant teachers in the course (see Fig 2.) which indicates and affirmation. To further triangulate the survey responses on learning outcomes provide deeper insights of this primary objective of this course. An overwhelming majority (88%) of respondent teachers indicated that they felt confident or very confident about hardware and software components in a school ICT lab setup. Only 6.7% teachers did not feel confident in handling the hardware and software components.

Fig. 4. How confident you are now with regard to the topics you have learned in the course E09-ICT Lab in School?

Similarly, as depicted in Fig 5. Most of the teachers expressed confidence and readiness to take steps which can keep the ICT lab functioning in their schools. That means the teachers were able to successfully don the hat of a troubleshooter! This is a significant finding. Perhaps this manifests TK (technological knowledge) of TPACK.

Fig. 5. How do you plan to practically implement the learnings in the course? (can choose multiple)

In regards with the quality of engagement on LMS discussion forum and CoP the observations have been of varied and mixed kinds. Further analysis is required to identify patterns and draw any conclusions.

Overall, 95% of respondents reported having a good or very experience while taking the course. The respondents also suggested some new topics to be included mostly catering to their subject domain teaching. Importantly, many respondents and participants strongly suggested to conduct few face-to-face hands-on sessions (as was envisaged while designing the course in the beginning).

A. Effectiveness and limitations of the model

The ICT Lab in School TPD course was not just a course for teachers professional development but a model for sustaining and maintaining essential EdTech infrastructure in schools. The findings from the above pilot implementation indicate that the model has found resonance with teachers. That is, teachers have found it useful to know the basic troubleshooting skills to maintain the ICT lab in their schools. However, since the course was offered during the COVID-19 pandemic when ICT labs in schools were still closed it could not be ascertained whether teachers were indeed able to activate lab and make them functional. However, the course performance of participating teachers and their responses in the survey positively indicate the effective potential of this model – teachers as troubleshooters. Needless to say, the argument of teachers as troubleshooters should not be misconstrued as an attempt to render teachers as technicians or overburden an already crammed schedule of teachers. Instead, the argument and experiment done in this TPD course should be viewed from a digital agency perspective [9]. Digital agency includes competence, confidence and accountability with respect to technology. Troubleshooting is an advanced and higher order skill. It goes beyond literacy. It is about critical understanding of technology. Therefore, by developing the ability to critically understand the available educational technology and ICT lab, teachers become empowered to not only keep the technology functional but also will become empowered to assess, evaluate, select as well as reject EdTech as per their relevance, affordance and pedagogical practices [10], [11].

IV. CONCLUSION

On the one hand the ICT Lab in School TPD course was an experiment to address the common challenge of dysfunctional school ICT labs. On the other hand, this was also a model to demonstrate ways to cultivate teachers' agency - to own, sustain and nurture school ICT lab as an active space for innovative teaching and learning. The simple, easy to understand low threshold high ceiling design and structure of course seemed to have resonated with the needs and requirements of teachers to keep up with the technological advancements. While a component to ascertain learning outcomes in terms of ground level realities i.e. status of ICT lab in the schools of participating teachers would have given a more reliable sense; nevertheless, the high passing percentage, participation in peer graded assessments for asynchronous activities/practicum and self reported data do indicate the need, relevance and effectiveness of such a TPD model to keep ICT and EdTech infrastructure in schools functional and thriving.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE PRACTICE AND RESEARCH

- In order to make the teachers efficient and have the effective use of the ICT labs in the school for daily teaching and learning process, teachers should go through such TPD courses that upskill and empower them.
- Ability to troubleshoot and critically understand technology leads to empowerment of teachers and enables them to select, reject or adapt EdTech; this ability can also help to avoid water-tight dependencies on technology vendors and enhances usability.
- Teachers should be encouraged to create help

materials and resources on troubleshooting and make those available to other fellow teachers for ready reference.

- Availability of such modular online courses will enable teachers to take advantage of such opportunities; a mix of self paced and open runs, possibly in multiple indian languages will provide more freedom and flexibility for teachers and educators to build their capacities to leverage ICTs and educational technology more meaningfully and confidently.
- Despite teachers' upskilling it is imperative on the government to allocate adequate funds to ensure upkeep, functioning and upgradation of ICT infrastructure in schools.

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